

Preparation of Ecotourism Development Strategy in Sungai Langka Village, Gedong Tataan District, Pesawaran, Lampung Province

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ABSTRACT

Published Online: 24 April, 2024

Tourism is all activities related to tourism and is multidimensional and multidisciplinary in nature which emerges as a manifestation of the needs of each person and country as well as interactions between tourists and local communities, fellow tourists, local governments and entrepreneurs. Factors that influence ecotourism development strategies come from within and outside the tourist attraction with a focus on efforts to encourage sustainable tourism. Tourism village planning should also be followed by the development of human resources and tourism supporting facilities while still paying attention to environmental elements. One of the areas in Lampung Province that is developing regional potential in the tourism sector is Pesawaran regency. Sungai Langka village is one of the villages with potential for ecotourism in Pesawaran district. This research aims to analyze ecotourism development strategies in Sungai Langka Pesawaran Village, Lampung. The research method uses SWOT analysis to determine the internal and external factors of tourist villages with the QSPM matrix to determine the development priority scale. Data collection was carried out through direct observation and distributing questionnaires to village officials, village communities, visitors and local government agencies. The results of this research are regarding the form of ecotourism development strategy that will be used to increase the role of tourism in Gedong Tataan.

KEYWORDS:

Ecotourism, Strategy, SWOT, QSPM

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is developed to be able to encourage economic activities and improve the image of the Indonesian state, improve the welfare of local communities and provide expansion of employment opportunities with tourism development that utilizes the diversity of natural beauty charms and national potential (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 17 of 2007 concerning the National Long-Term Development Plan 2005-2025). Tourism development should be based on tourism planning that considers elements of sustainability, the environment, the use of space in tourism destinations, and synergy between stakeholders, especially industry, government and society (Fandeli Chafid, 2000).

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**Cite this Article: Dina Mariana Sari, Zainal Abidin, Ahmad Herison (2024). Preparation of Ecotourism Development Strategy in Sungai Langka Village, Gedong Tataan District, Pesawaran, Lampung Province. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(4), 317-325*

Tourism development frequently uses multiple terms like green tourism, fair trade tourism, sustainable tourism, ecotourism, alternative tourism etc. to depict its meaningful interventions (Sariskumar & Bhavan, 2018). Tourism has differences in characteristics, especially ecotourism, sustainable development is an organized integrated effort to develop quality of life by regulating the provision, development, utilization and maintenance of natural resources in a sustainable manner and increasing productive creative economic activities in the tourism sector (Ratnawati, 2023). The ecotourism approach is carried out through the development of tourism concepts that can have a long-term impact both on the environment, social, culture, and economy for the present and future for all local communities and tourists who visit (Kia, 2021). For this reason, tourism needs to be encouraged to be more focused for a more planned future. Lampung Province as the gateway to Sumatra, is the closest alternative area for tourists from or outside the city to find new tourist destinations. The pattern of tourist destinations today continues to develop with a variety of

themes from offering natural beauty, forests, beaches, agriculture, plantations to education in the form of interesting attractions that visitors can get while in tourist sites. One of the regions in Lampung Province that is developing regional potential in the field of tourism is Pesawaran Regency with a focus on agricultural and plantation products as superior natural products, natural beauty, and cultural distinctiveness with a unique variety of Lampung embroidery motifs. Currently, the principle of ecotourism is needed for environmental sustainability, regional planning, especially in the field of tourism. Ecotourism focuses on three main issues, namely natural or ecological sustainability, the creation of economic benefits, and acceptance in the social life of the community. Therefore, ecotourism offers every tourist the opportunity to see, feel and enjoy the natural, spiritual and cultural experiences of the local people. Ecotourism activities can increase local economic income which is used as an ecotourism destination and generate economic benefits for the lives of people living in the area and its surroundings. Gedong Tataan District is one of eleven sub-districts in Pesawaran regency and is the capital of Pesawaran. Gedong Tataan has several destinations or tourist attractions, both natural attractions and educational tourist destinations. The development of plantation areas into tourism, especially in Pesawaran regency, may already exist but the community has not focused much on ecotourism, some sources stated in previous research that ecotourism with various possible methods is used as a direction in tourism development. So that on this occasion, it was used to develop the presentation of ecotourism development strategies in Gedong Tataan sub-district with a case study of Sungai Langka village studies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Ecotourism

Historically, ecotourism originated in Kenya, Africa in the 1970s (Syah & Said, 2020). At that time it was known as the most expensive tourism because of its activities that were hunting wildlife. In 1976, Gerardo Budowski tried to combine nature tourism and conservation as one. In Indonesia, ecotourism was introduced by several foreign travel agencies in the 1980s, one example of which made Kerinci active volcano climbing activities, and Toba volcanic lake visits. This ecotourism activity formally received support from the government with the birth of Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism. Furthermore, in a more general concept, ecotourism has the meaning of having meaning as environmentally friendly tourism. Ecotourism has a concern not to fill leisure time while enjoying beauty, but includes learning. The basic principle of ecotourism further develops, namely as nature-based tourism that includes education and protection (conservation) of the natural environment, which is managed by prioritizing a sustainable development (Mirhosseini, 2020).

The following are some definitions of ecotourism put forward by previous researchers. Although each other has differences, all of them have a common thread that leads to the same context, including the following:

- a. Ecotourism or ecotourism is one of the environmentally friendly tourism activities by prioritizing aspects of nature conservation, aspects of socio-cultural, economic empowerment of local communities, and aspects of learning and education (Adharani, 2020)
- b. Ecotourism is nature-based tourism by including aspects of education and interpretation of the natural environment and culture of the community with ecological sustainability management (Tri, 2014)
- c. Ecotourism is a term and concept that connects tourism with conservation. Ecotourism is environmentally friendly tourism and is a type of tourism that prioritizes tourist responsibility to the environment (Ayustia & Nadapdap, 2023).
- d. Ecotourism is a tourism business activity that can provide many benefits, such as funding sources for conservation areas, protection of conservation areas, alternative sources of livelihood for local communities, options to promote conservation, and encouragement of conservation efforts specifically (Regina & Butarbutar, 2021).
- e. Ecotourism is a model of responsible natural tourism in unspoiled areas or naturally managed areas that have the aim of enjoying natural beauty by involving elements of education and support for conservation efforts and increasing the economic income of local communities (Syah & Said, 2020).
- f. Ecotourism is indigenous natural tourism that is responsible, respectful and preserving the environment and improving the welfare of local residents (Andriani & Gde Pitana, 2020). Ecotourism focuses on three main things, namely natural or ecological sustainability, providing economic benefits, and psychologically acceptable in the social life of the community. So, ecotourism activities directly give access to everyone to see, know and enjoy the natural, intellectual and cultural experiences of local communities. Ecotourism activities can increase income for nature conservation which is used as an ecotourism tourism object and generate economic benefits for the lives of people in the location or local area.

According to the Directorate General of Destination Development, Tourism of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, and WWF-Indonesia (2009) ecotourism has five principles as follows:

1. Nature-based. Nature-based is products and markets based on nature. Nature tourism is part or whole of nature itself. Natural resource conservation is fundamental in the development and management of natural tourism.
2. Ecologically sustainable. Ecological stability is the planning and management of ecologically sustainable areas. All environmental functions, both biological, physical, and social, continue to run well.
3. Environmentally educative. Environmental education is intended for managers and visitors. Education is the core of ecotourism that distinguishes it from other natural attractions. Education creates an atmosphere that is fun, meaningful, caring, and appreciative of the environment. Environmental sustainability in the long term can run with educational activities.
4. Beneficial for local communities. These benefits can be direct or indirect. Direct benefits include, among others, the community involved in tourist activities, services to tourists, and sales of goods needed by tourists. Indirect benefits in the form of increased insight from tourists or managers.
5. Satisfaction for tourists. Satisfaction is the fulfillment of tourists' expectations of everything that is offered.

- b. Strategy
- Strategy is a series of commitment or integrated actions, formulated to exploit core competence and achieve competitive advantage. Strategy as target formulation and long-term objective of an organization, actions direction, and also required resources to achieve the target (Putra & Nasution, 2018).

III. METHODS

A. Type of research

In this study using a type of qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative method is a research method that involves the process of interaction between the author and the subject being analyzed, among others, by conducting interviews, and direct observation at the research location (Sugiyono, 2013). From these results, you will get a descriptive narrative. Qualitative research is directed at the development of ecotourism as an influence of application on the function of public space, and the sustainability of existing tourism. This research is said to be qualitative research because the results of this research are obtained through directed discussions to get an overview of the internal and external factors owned at the research location.

B. Research Location

In this study, the research location was taken located in Sungai Langka village at Gedong Tataan, Pesawaran Lampung.

Figure 1. Location Map

C. Tools and Materials

The materials and tools used in this study include village thematic maps, GPS (Global Positioning System), cameras, cell phones, interview questionnaires, and computers.

D. Data Resources

The data collection process will include:

a. Primary data

To obtain primary data, data obtained from the field were collected, using the following methods:

1. Interview

The target of the interview comes from village, community, or certain community officials in the area. In collecting data, instruments or tools in the form of questionnaires are needed to progress facilitate. The content of the survey includes observing, collecting information, filming, taking photos and exchanging ideas with local authorities, people, tourism staff and tourists at potential tourism development destinations. community. The survey method by questionnaire was conducted at the same time as the field survey. The sampling method used is the convenience sampling method applied to tourists and the stratified sampling method applied to local people (Huyen Trang, 2023).

2. Observation

Observation is a data collection method used to collect data through observation and sensing (Mirhosseini, 2020).

Observations focused on physical, economic, and social conditions in Sungai Langka village

b. Secondary data

Methods carried out in secondary data collection include:

1. Literature Study

Literature study is a method of collecting data by reading, studying, and understanding theories and literature related to discussion. The literature study studied can be in the form of research, books, or other scientific works.

2. Internet material search methods. The search method in question is the procedure for searching data through media such as the internet or other network media that provide facilities in the network. Thus, it is possible to be able to utilize the general state data of the research location and information quickly and easily.

E. Analysis methods

In this study, SWOT analysis, which is a situation analysis, was used as a method in order to achieve the purpose of the study in terms of content and scope.

1. SWOT Analysis

This analysis is one of the strategic planning methods to describe conditions and evaluate a problem in planning based on internal factors (inside) and external factors (outside), namely strength, weakness, opportunities and threats or called situation analysis. The approach used is the SWOT Analysis Model because the preparation process is relatively simple, participatory, qualitative types of information are needed in the preparation, and can be applied to various sectors / fields, generic in nature, such as economic, socio-cultural, and environmental (Hakim & Agustiani, 2022). The division of strategic factors in SWOT analysis (Maruf, 2022) are:

- a. Strength factor. What is meant by the strength factors possessed by a company including business units in it are, among others, special competition contained in the organization which results in having a comparative advantage by business units in the market. This is because the business unit has a source of skills, reliable products and so on that makes it stronger than competitors in satisfying market needs that

have been and are planned to be served by the business unit concerned.

- b. Weakness factor. What is meant by weakness is a limitation or deficiency in terms of resources, skills, and abilities that become a serious obstacle to the appearance of satisfactory organizational performance.
- c. Opportunity factor. The definition of opportunities is simply that opportunities are various environmental situations that are favorable to a business unit.
- d. Threat factors. The definition of threat is the opposite of the notion of opportunity, namely environmental factors that do not benefit a business unit if not overcome the threat will become a danger to the business unit concerned both now and in the future.

The shape of the SWOT matrix can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. SWOT Matrix Shape (Rangkuti, 2017)

	<i>Strengths (S)</i>	<i>Weakness (W)</i>
SWOT	Determine the 5 factors that are strengths	Determine 5 factors that are weakness
<i>Opportunities (O)</i>	Strategy (SO)	Strategy (WO)
Determine the 5 factors that become opportunities	Create strategies that use power to seize opportunities	Create strategies that minimize weakness to take advantage of opportunities
<i>Threats (T)</i>	Strategy (ST)	Strategy (WT)
Determine the 5 factors that are strengths	Create strategies that use power to seize threats	Create strategies that minimize weakness to avoid threats

2. QSPM Analysis

Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) is one approach Strategy management with a function to evaluate opportunities from one strategy. The Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix is a strategic tool which is used to evaluate alternative set of strategies. The QSPM incorporate earlier stage details in an organize way to calculate the score of multiple strategies in order to find the best match strategy for the organization this strategic management tool is one of the most important tool

for the construction industry for the effective preparation of plans and goal of the organization (Abenezer&Kebede,2021). The preparation of marketing strategies is carried out using three stages of data analysis implementation (Saputro, 2021), namely:

a. The Input Stage

At this stage, data can be divided into two, namely external data and internal data. Information on strategic factors that have been identified in the field observation process is arranged into two types of matrices, namely: External Factor Evaluation (EFE) and Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE). The EFE matrix is used to determine the biggest and smallest opportunities that the company has and the biggest threats and threats that do not affect the company, while the IFE matrix is used to determine the biggest and smallest strengths owned and the biggest and smallest weaknesses that the company has.

b. The Matching Stage

In this second stage, an analysis process is carried out to formulate a company strategy through two stages. The first stage is to determine the Internal and External Matrix (IE). The IE matrix serves to position a company into a matrix consisting of nine cells. From these results, it will be possible to identify how the company's current position is, so that it can make it easier to formulate a company strategy. The matrix will produce a more comprehensive business strategy for the company. The second stage is to create a SWOT (Strength-Weakness-Opportunity-Threads) Matrix. The SWOT matrix used here is a SWOT matrix that is not comprehensive or a matrix for one company.

c. Decision Stage

In this last step, several alternative strategies are raised from the results of the previous analysis. The method that can be used in this last step is the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM). QSPM is a matrix for the completion of a framework in the analysis process of best strategizing (Jozi & Rezaian, 2010). This technique clearly shows the best alternative strategy to choose. The QSPM matrix helps management to choose the best strategy based on alternative strategies are sourced from the EFE and EFI matrix.

1. Identify internal (strength and weakness) and external (opportunity and threat) factors.
2. Give weight to each factor.
3. Find several alternative strategies that allow it to be run.
4. Determine the value of attractiveness scores (AS) by reflecting on all factors for each strategy. The provisions of the US value are as follows:
Value 1 = Not interesting
Value 1 = Slightly interesting
Value 1 = Interesting
Value 1 = Very interesting
5. Calculates the total attractiveness scores (TAS) value by multiplying the weight by the AS.
6. Calculates all TAS values on each factor in each strategy.
7. Decision. The largest total TAS value indicates the best recommended strategy to execute.

IV. RESULTS

A. SWOT Analysis

The calculation of the weight score in IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary) is generated from the multiplication between the weight value and the rating. Details of IFAS in the field of tourism in Sungai Langka village in Gedong Tataan settings can be seen in the following table:

Table 2. IFAS Matrix

N o	Internal Factors	Value	Rating	Score	Rank
A Strength					
1	Citizen Support	0,10	4	0,40	3
2	The existence of a typical culture of the Lampung region	0,10	4	0,41	2
3	The existence of tourist spots of historical value	0,10	4	0,40	4
4	There is a natural attraction	0,10	4	0,41	1
5	There is BUMDES	0,11	2	0,21	5
Total		1		1,84	

Step by step making the QSPM matrix as follows (Khoerul ummah, 2022):

No	Internal Factors	Value	Rating	Score	Rank
B Weakness					
1	Education Background	0,05	3	0,14	5
2	Ecotourism knowledge	0,07	4	0,28	4
3	Accessibility not supported	0,14	3	0,41	1
4	Infrastructure limitations	0,13	3	0,39	2
5	Preservation of historical objects	0,10	3	0,31	3
Total		1		1,53	

The calculation of the weight score in EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary) is generated from the multiplication between the weight value and the rating. Details of EFAS in tourism in Sungai Langka village in Gedong Tataan settings can be seen in the following table:

Table 3. EFAS Matrix

No	External Factors	Value	Rating	Score	Rank
A Opportunity					
1	Local government support	0,13	3	0,40	2
2	New Travel desires	0,04	3	0,14	5
3	Potential locations	0,09	4	0,36	3
4	Promoted media	0,09	3	0,27	4
5	No other ecotourism yet	0,13	5	0,68	1
Total		1		1,87	
B Threats					
1	Promotion capabilities	0,04	2	0,09	5

2	Development of tourist attraction	0,13	3	0,34	1
3	Government policy	0,09	3	0,23	3
4	Digital technology	0,09	2	0,14	4
5	Lack of information	0,13	2	0,31	2
Total		1		1,12	

Based on the table above, it is known that the total opportunity score is 1.76 and the total threat score is 1.67. The total EFAS score of 0.09 is derived from subtracting the total opportunity score by the total threat score. In the SWOT analysis, a total IFAS score of 0.30 and a total EFAS score of 0.09 were obtained. From the total IFAS and EFAS scores, a reference point will be formed for the SWOT quadrant matrix to determine the company's position. Thus, the author can make recommendations for development strategies from the position. The SWOT quadrant matrix can be seen in Figure 3 based on Figure 3, it can be seen that Sungai Langka Village tourism is in a position between the Opportunity and Strength axes, namely Quadrant I. That is, the village that is used as a case study is advised to carry out a progressive strategy by utilizing the internal strengths of the village to benefit from external opportunities to achieve increased business growth. The next stage to determine the priority development strategy is used SWOT analysis which is a continuation of the assessment analysis. Furthermore, the strategy of developing plantation tourism in Gedong Tataan can be seen from the following SWOT analysis matrix:

Table 4. Matrix SWOT

	STRENGTH (S)	WEAKNESS (W)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive public perception of tourism villages • The existence of a typical culture of the Lampung region • The existence of tourist spots of historical value • Has natural potential as well as unique 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The enthusiasm of the village community tends to be temporary • The education background of the villagers is still low • There has been no periodic promotion by

	tourist attractions • The existence of economic support from the BUMDES Community	the community or village officials • Some accessibility conditions are not supported
OPPORTUNITIES (O)	STRATEGY (S-O)	STRATEGY (W-O)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has tourism potential to be developed cultural elements typical of Lampung The opening of employment opportunities and increasing the empowerment of rural communities There is government support for tourism development The development of promotional media to market the tourism industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By utilizing information technology and social media in an effort to promote the potential of tourist attractions. Improvement of tourist objects and attractions Utilization of tourism awareness group programs to develop tourism potential Create a special gallery of Jelujur Embroidery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attract private parties or investors in collaboration with the surrounding community by utilizing the distinctive potential of each village Improve human resources (HR) who are experts in the field of tourism
THREATS(T)	STRATEGY (S-T)	STRATEGY (W-T)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inconvenient road access Lack of marketing skills of tourism actors at the village level Lack of understanding about ecotourism in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving road access with local government support Create the guidance directives of ecotourism 	Strengthening the role of village officials and the government on socializing the importance of protecting the environment

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is no direction of government policy on ecotourism 		
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B. QSPM Analysis

After the input stage, internal and external environment analysis through IFAS and EFAS and the next SWOT matrix stage is the stage of taking four priorities using QSPM to objectively determine among alternative strategies. Based on the results of the QSPM assessment, the order of the four highest TAS values is taken to produce alternative priority strategies that can be implemented in ecotourism development in Sungai Langka village.

Table 5. Priority Scale

Priority	Score	Information
1	5,98	Utilizing information technology and social media in an effort to promote the potential of tourist attractions
2	6,45	Improvement of tourist objects and attractions
3	6,67	Utilization of tourism awareness group programs to develop tourism potential
4	6,80	Create a special gallery of Jelujur Embroidery

Factor	Value	Strategy				
		Strategy 1		Strategy 2		
		AS1	TAS1	AS2	TAS2	
Internal Factor						
Strength	A	0,10	4	0,40	4	0,40
	B	0,10	3	0,31	4	0,41
	C	0,10	4	0,40	4	0,40
	D	0,10	4	0,41	4	0,41
	E	0,11	1	0,11	1	0,11
	F	0,05	3	0,14	3	0,14
	G	0,07	2	0,14	3	0,21
Weakness	H	0,14	2	0,27	2	0,27
	I	0,13	2	0,26	4	0,53
	J	0,10	4	0,42	4	0,42
External Factor						
Opportunity	A	0,09	4	0,36	4	0,36
	B	0,07	4	0,30	4	0,30
	C	0,11	1	0,11	2	0,22
	D	0,09	4	0,38	4	0,38

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Threats	E	0,11	4	0,43	4	0,43
	F	0,10	4	0,40	3	0,30
	G	0,10	1	0,10	2	0,20
	H	0,12	2	0,24	3	0,36
	I	0,10	4	0,41	2	0,20
	J	0,10	4	0,40	4	0,40
Total				5,98	6,45	

Factor	Value	Strategy				
		Strategy 3		Strategy 4		
		AS3	TAS3	AS4	TAS4	
Internal Factor						
Strength	A	0,10	4	0,40	4	0,40
	B	0,10	3	0,31	4	0,41
	C	0,10	4	0,40	4	0,40
	D	0,10	4	0,41	1	0,10
	E	0,11	4	0,43	3	0,32
	F	0,05	3	0,14	3	0,14
Weakness	G	0,07	4	0,28	4	0,28
	H	0,14	3	0,41	3	0,41
	I	0,13	4	0,53	4	0,53
	J	0,10	4	0,42	4	0,42
External Factor						
Opportunity	A	0,09	3	0,27	4	0,36
	B	0,07	4	0,30	3	0,22
	C	0,11	2	0,22	4	0,44
	D	0,09	4	0,38	4	0,38
	E	0,11	3	0,32	4	0,43
	F	0,10	3	0,30	3	0,30
	G	0,10	2	0,20	2	0,20
Threats	H	0,12	3	0,36	3	0,36
	I	0,10	3	0,31	3	0,31
	J	0,10	3	0,30	4	0,40
Total				6,67	6,80	

Factor	Value	Strategy 5		
		AS5	TAS5	
Internal Factor				
Strength	A	0,10	4	0,40
	B	0,10	1	0,10
	C	0,10	4	0,40
	D	0,10	3	0,31
	E	0,11	2	0,21

Weakness	F	0,05	2	0,09
	G	0,07	4	0,28
	H	0,14	4	0,54
	I	0,13	4	0,53
	J	0,10	4	0,42
	External Factor			
Opportunity	A	0,09	4	0,36
	B	0,07	4	0,30
	C	0,11	4	0,44
	D	0,09	4	0,38
	E	0,11	4	0,43
	F	0,10	3	0,30
	G	0,10	2	0,20
Threats	H	0,12	4	0,48
	I	0,10	2	0,20
	J	0,10	4	0,40
Total				6,78

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted in Sungai Langka village, Gedong Tataan District as a case study, regarding the study of ecotourism potential, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Sungai Langka Village has various ecotourism potentials to be developed. These potentials include natural potential in the form of views of natural beauty from unspoiled plantations. The potential of flora such as horticultural crops, cocoa, salak to oranges is used by local villagers to be processed as additional income from the sale of raw materials to finished materials. Cultural potential can be seen from the jelujur embroidery group accompanied by Pokdarwis (Tourism Awareness Group) as a typical cultural heritage of Lampung and finally the potential of material heritage in the form of baths from the Dutch era known as Pekon Janda in Sungai Langka Village.
2. Based on the results of IE analysis, it can be seen that the tourism position of Sungai Langka Village is in Quadrant I. That is, Sungai Langka village is advised to carry out a progressive strategy by utilizing the internal strength of the village to benefit from external opportunities to achieve increased business growth. This strategy can be interpreted as strengthening the variables of strength owned and developing quality such as the quality of human resources, increasing accreditation of tourist attractions, and strengthening cultural elements.
3. Alternative priority strategies that can be used for ecotourism development successively based on the results of the QSPM analysis assessment are utilizing information technology and social media in an effort to promote the potential of tourist attractions, increasing tourist

attraction, utilizing tourism awareness group programs to develop tourism potential, and creating a special gallery of Sulam Jelujur as a reinforcement in the field of Lampung's distinctive culture as part of the focus of ecotourism issues.

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